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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF DISCURSIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article explores the importance of developing discourse competence in foreign language education for students. In the context of growing international collaboration and the global labor market, medical professionals are expected to communicate effectively in foreign languages. The study distinguishes between the concepts of “competence” and “competency,” emphasizing the need for not only knowledge but also practical communication skills. It also defines discourse as a communicative phenomenon that includes both verbal and non-verbal aspects, contextual factors, and cultural appropriateness. Special attention is given to the integration of discourse-based approaches in foreign language instruction, highlighting their effectiveness in training competent medical specialists capable of participating in international academic and professional settings.

Key words: discursive competence, non-philological education, competence, competency, communicative approach.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada talabalarni xorijiy tilga o'qitishda diskursiv kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning ahamiyati yoritiladi. Xalqaro hamkorlikning kengayishi va global mehnat bozori sharoitida tibbiyot mutaxassislaridan xorijiy tillarda samarali muloqot qila olish talab etiladi. Tadqiqotda “kompetensiya” va “kompetentlik” tushunchalari farqlanib, nafaqat nazariy bilim, balki amaliy kommunikativ ko'nikmalarning ham zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Shuningdek, diskurs verbal va noverbal jihatlari, kontekstual omillar hamda madaniy moslikni o'z ichiga oluvchi kommunikativ hodisa sifatida talqin etiladi. Xorijiy til ta'limida diskursga asoslangan yondashuvlarni integratsiya qilishga alohida e'tibor qaratilib, ularning xalqaro akademik va kasbiy muhitda faol ishtirok eta oladigan kompetent tibbiyot mutaxassislarini tayyorlashdagi samaradorligi ko'rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: diskursiv kompetensiya, nofilologik ta'lim, kompetensiya, kompetentlik, kommunikativ yondashuv.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение развития дискурсивной компетентности студентов в процессе обучения иностранному языку. В условиях расширяющегося международного сотрудничества и глобального рынка труда от медицинских специалистов требуется умение эффективно общаться на иностранных языках. В исследовании разграничиваются понятия “компетенция” и “компетентность”, при этом подчеркивается необходимость не только теоретических знаний, но и практических коммуникативных навыков. Также дискурс определяется как коммуникативное явление, включающее вербальные и невербальные аспекты, контекстуальные факторы и культурную уместность. Особое внимание уделяется интеграции дискурсивно-ориентированных подходов в преподавание иностранных языков, поскольку они способствуют подготовке компетентных медицинских специалистов, способных участвовать в международной академической и профессиональной среде.

Ключевые слова: дискурсивная компетентность, нефилологическое образование, компетенция, компетентность, коммуникативный подход.

INTRODUCTION

International collaboration is growing across all areas of knowledge, and the current global job market demands that graduates of higher medical institutions be more than just experts in their specific fields. They must also be well-rounded professionals who are proficient in foreign languages, enabling them to communicate effectively on an international level.

A competent professional should possess the ability to communicate fluently in foreign languages with colleagues from various countries, engage in discussions on advancements in medicine while considering current trends, deliver presentations at international medical congresses, symposiums, and conferences, and appropriately adapt their language use to fit different communicative contexts.

For this reason, it is essential to enhance future physicians' proficiency in foreign language communication in line with the Common European Framework of Reference. This requires developing new approaches to teaching foreign languages as a mandatory subject in higher non-philological education. It is also necessary to implement interactive teaching methods and technologies that support the development of verbal discursive skills in a foreign language, grounded in the systematic acquisition of knowledge throughout the educational process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of discursive competence has become an important research focus in foreign language education, especially in the context of professionally oriented language training. Scholars emphasize that modern specialists should not only possess linguistic knowledge but also be able to use language appropriately in real communicative situations. Khutorskii distinguishes between "competence" as a set of knowledge, skills, abilities, and methods of activity and "competency" as the practical realization of these qualities in personal and professional contexts [1].

This distinction is significant for foreign language teaching because it shows that students must move beyond theoretical knowledge toward active communicative performance. Yefimova also underlines the importance of foreign language communicative competence in professional education, noting that it includes both activity-based and communicative components necessary for effective interaction in a professional environment [2].

In this regard, discursive competence is closely connected with the ability to construct coherent, logical, and contextually appropriate speech. Brown defines discourse as the ability to connect sentences into meaningful and coherent communicative units [3].

Similarly, Canale and Swain consider discourse competence an essential component of communicative competence since it enables learners to produce and interpret texts according to communicative goals and social context [4].

Krychina further notes that text serves as a primary source of discourse information and functions as a central unit in teaching professional foreign language communication [5].

Therefore, the literature shows that the development of discursive competence is essential for preparing students, particularly future medical specialists, for effective participation in international academic and professional communication.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on a qualitative and comparative analysis of scientific literature related to discursive competence in foreign language education. The research employed methods such as comparative analysis, theoretical review, synthesis, and generalization. Through the comparative analysis method, different scholarly interpretations of the concepts of "competence," "competency," and "discursive competence" were examined and contrasted. Relevant academic sources, including works by Khutorskii, Yefimova, Brown, Canale, Swain, and Krychina, were analyzed to identify the main theoretical approaches to discourse-oriented language teaching.

The method of synthesis was used to integrate various theoretical perspectives and establish a comprehensive understanding of discursive competence as a component of communicative competence. In addition, the generalization method enabled the identification of common principles and pedagogical implications for developing students' foreign language communication skills. The findings obtained through these methods provide a theoretical foundation for emphasizing discourse-based approaches in foreign language instruction, particularly in the preparation of future medical professionals for effective participation in International academic and professional communication.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The goal of foreign language learning in higher education is not only to acquire the language as a means of communication but also to develop professionally oriented foreign language competence, enabling future specialists to perform their professional duties effectively.

The concepts of "competence" and "competency" are viewed and interpreted differently by various scholars depending on their disciplinary perspectives.

Andrii Khutorskii makes a clear distinction between the terms “competence” and “competency.” According to him:

1. Competence refers to a set of interrelated human characteristics, such as knowledge, abilities, skills, and methods of activity, that are necessary for effective performance in a specific area.
2. Competency, on the other hand, is defined as the actual possession and demonstration of that competence by a person, and it also includes the individual’s personal attitudes, values, and feelings toward the subject or activity in question ^[1].

In short, competence is the potential, while competency is the realized and personal expression of that potential in real-world contexts.

According to the definitions of these terms, competence should be understood as a clearly defined requirement or standard that determines the expected educational level of future physicians. In contrast, competency refers to the actually developed personal qualities and minimal practical experience that a student possesses. Foreign communicative competence is considered an integral component of a specialist’s professional activity. It comprises several substructures:

1. Activity component: Includes knowledge, abilities, skills, and methods required to perform professional tasks.
2. Communicative component: Encompasses knowledge, abilities, skills, and strategies necessary for effective professional communication.

This highlights the importance of not only acquiring theoretical knowledge but also developing practical communication skills in a foreign language, which are essential in today’s global medical environment ^[2].

The discourse component refers to the set of rules that govern how meaning is constructed within a specific type of speech or communication. Discourse represents a form of communicative meaning—that is, not only what should be said but also how it should be expressed. It is always directed toward an interlocutor, listener, or reader.

Discourse is characterized by several key features:

These features are particularly important in written discourse, where lexical and grammatical connections, the logical structure of meaning, and the effective organization of speech are more critical than in spoken interaction.

In modern linguistics, discourse is defined as a complex communicative phenomenon that encompasses not only the text itself but also extralinguistic factors such as background knowledge, worldviews, and the intentions and attitudes of the speaker or listener, which are essential for the accurate interpretation of a message. Unlike a simple text, discourse is primarily seen as an example of how specific communicative intentions are realized within a particular communicative context and in interaction with a specific interlocutor who may belong to a different cultural background. This interaction involves both verbal and non-verbal means, tailored to the given situation. The appropriateness and effectiveness of a speaker’s language behavior within discourse are judged by the success of the communication, i.e., whether the intended communicative goal was achieved, and by how well it aligns with the norms of verbal and non-verbal behavior typical for a particular linguocultural community.

A new approach to defining discourse has largely emerged within the field of foreign language teaching. According to foreign scholars, discourse competence is understood as both the knowledge of various discourse types and their structural principles, as well as the ability to construct and interpret discourse appropriately based on different communicative contexts ^[4].

H. Douglas Brown described discourse as the human ability to link sentences into coherent discourse segments, thereby producing a semantically meaningful text from a collection of individual phrases ^[3].

This discourse-based approach to studying linguistic phenomena has significantly influenced the methods and techniques used in foreign language instruction, as it emphasizes the procedural and functional unity of language behavior by integrating both verbal and non-verbal components. As a result, the concept of the text—viewed as a central communicative unit and a complex semiotic structure formed through semantic elements aligned by the author's communicative intention—has gained prominence in foreign language education. As noted by Kruchyna, the text serves as a primary source of discourse information and is now widely recognized in theory and practice as the core unit for teaching language communication ^[5].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Discourse competence refers to a person's ability to produce coherent and connected speech, taking into account grammatical, lexical, and syntactic rules, as well as the communicative context and extralinguistic factors, which are essential elements of the communication process. It involves logically organizing utterances into complete texts and presenting them in line with the appropriate speech style and principles of rhetorical effectiveness.

In the development of students' foreign language competence, there is a noticeable shift in focus: from simply using the text as a model of discourse forms in spoken communication to emphasizing the strategies and means of expressing and achieving communicative goals with an interlocutor.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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